

of ground mycelia within a day. The procedure is outlined below.

Grow hyphal cultures in 50 ml of Fries medium in 125-ml flasks at 30 °C with shaking. After 5-10 d, harvest the mycelia by suction and lyophilize them. Grind the dried mycelia finely using a mortar and pestle with liquid N or, alternatively, with a few grains of sterile acid-washed sand. If stored at -20 °C with a desiccant, the mycelial powder will keep for several months.

For a single extraction, suspend 50-75 mg of pulverized mycelia in 750 µl extraction buffer (100 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8; 100 mM EDTA; and 250 mM NaCl) by light vortexing in a 1.5-ml microcentrifuge tube. The needed amount of mycelia powder will fill about a quarter of the tube. Add 75 µl 10% (wt/vol) SDS; mix the contents gently and incubate for at least 30 min at 65 °C. Then add 300 µl potassium acetate solution (3 M potassium acetate-2 M acetic acid, pH 4.8), mix gently by inversion, and incubate the tube on ice for 15 min. Spin down precipitate (proteins and detergent) and debris at 13,000 rpm for 15 min.

Carefully transfer 750 µl of supernatant to a fresh tube containing 750 µl 2-propanol. (If a cleaner preparation is needed, the supernatant may be extracted with an equal volume of 24:1 (vol/vol) chloroform-isoamyl alcohol prior to alcohol precipitation.) Invert the tube to mix. Keep the tube on ice for 10 min, or longer if precipitation of nucleic acids is not satisfactory. Pellet down the nucleic acid (13,000 rpm for 5 min), wash with 70% ethanol, air-dry, and resuspend in 40 µl of TE buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.5-8; and 1 mM EDTA). This procedure will yield about 15 µg of DNA.

For a single Southern hybridization, use 1-3 µg of DNA per lane. DNA stored at 4 °C or lower will remain stable in TE buffer for several months. Contaminating RNA can be eliminated with RNase A (20 ng/µl final concentration) either during or after DNA restriction digestion. ■

Sclerotia of false smut (FSm) of rice from Assam, India

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Sclerotia of FSm *Claviceps oryzae sativae* Hashioka were found in Assam for the first time in late Nov 1991.

Less than 1% of the FSm spore balls in a rainfed lowland winter rice (Jul-Dec) crop had the sclerotia. They were borne as peelings from the surface of some spore balls and looked like petals of a flower bud (Fig. 1). Two sclerotia usually developed on a spore ball. They were never formed inside the spore balls.

Sclerotia were shed easily and were collected from the ground near rice hills. The largest sclerotium measured 14 × 7 mm, the smallest was 5 × 3 mm (Fig. 2).

The maximum and minimum temperatures during the week in which sclerotia developed ranged from 20 to 26 °C and from 11 to 15 °C, respectively. The relatively low temperatures during late Nov to early Dec induced sclerotia formation.

The sclerotia germinated after 3 mo when buried in sterile moist sand. They produced stalked stroma with plenty of ascospores.

FSm sclerotia were earlier reported in India at altitudes of 1,200 m and above in the hilly regions of the north where

1. Sclerotia of FSm borne on spore ball.

2. Sclerotia of FSm detached from spore ball.

temperate climate prevails. The sclerotia recently observed are in the plains region (Jorhat) at an altitude of 91 m. Sclerotia, through ascospores, can cause primary infection of rice. ■

A rapid method for DNA fingerprinting of the rice blast fungus *Pyricularia grisea*

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DNA fingerprinting and phylogenetic analysis based on the repetitive DNA probe MGR586 (Dupont) have been useful in studying the population structure of the rice blast fungus *P. grisea*. The DNA fingerprints are used to group isolates according to genetic similarity. The inference is that the groups share a common ancestor and,

Association between groups of isolates defined by RAPD (primer J-06) and RFLP (probe MGR586).^a

RFLP (MGR586)	RAPD (J-06)	Isolates (no.)
1, 1c, 1d, 1e	1	24
7, 7a	2	12
4, 4a, 4b, 4c	3, 4, 5	69
2	6	1
3	7	5
9	8	1
11	9	1
14	10	5
10	11	1
13	12	1

^aMGR586 designations with the same number and different letters are very similar but not identical (80% of bands in common). Each distinct profile produced by RAPD (J-06) was given a different number. Designations for groups of isolates are arbitrary.